

Women empowerment through Sustainable cereal production in tribal dominated regions of Koraput district of Odisha.

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Abstract

Agriculture and forestry are the life support system for tribals. Women were involved in agriculture since inception of tribal civilization. Our study included 4 revenue blocks namely Koraput, Jeypore, Kundra and Boipariguda of Koraput district of Odisha. About 120 women stake holders of farming families were interviewed by the use of PRA tools with pre-structured questionnaire. Rice, Finger millet and Maize were found to be the commonly cultivated cereals giving food, nutrition and livelihood support to them. Women were found to be the main stake holders in the entire agricultural operations. Basically, traditional farming practices followed by them meant for a low level sustainable production for year round consumption only. But, tribal woman in the age range of 20-35 were found to adopt for introduction of high yielding and resistant varieties which is contributing towards the enhancement of production as well as economic benefits. Production of Local and resistant high yielding varieties were compared with the use of both traditional and modern sustainable practices. But, due to poor infrastructure, economic instability, lack of knowledge in commercial scale cultivation, the production enhancement is not in par with the desired production in many cases. Statistical analysis using ANOVA pertaining to the data set showed the result at the level of significance $p < 0.01$. More Govt. and private sector participation can improve modern technical knowhow to combine the traditional agricultural practice with improved agro-economic practices to enhanced sustainable cereal production for livelihood, socio-economic development and vulnerable tribal women empowerment.

Key words. Women empowerment, Sustainable cereal production, tribal dominated, stake holders, Koraput district.

Introduction

World without women is just impossible as, they are central to origin, settlement and evolution of human civilization. Women are the backbone of the family, society, nation and the whole world. But, these communities are undervalued, underprivileged and underutilized resources in many parts of the world. But, due to some international effort and policy decisions the scenario is improving across many countries [7].

Tribal people have traditional wisdom and communities are intelligent enough to follow conventional agricultural practices following to make it sustainable by making a balance between livelihood and the environmental resource. They are optimistic about their future and hence protect their agriculture in sustainable manner but never become greedy to over exploitation of natural resources. Tribal women equally involved in agricultural activities at all stages from plantation to harvesting as well as post harvest processing.

Agriculture is stepping stone for survival but execute considerable impact on environment. This is induced by increase in human population where supply of quality and quantity of food. The challenges in terms of deficiencies for production, supply and consumption of adequate food still persists and hence livelihood is affected in greater way. Current estimation predicts that, due to rise in demand for food for rising global population the agricultural production is expected to increase. Foods become more affordable due to increase in income of households. Changes in production and prices of agricultural commodities will mostly affect the vulnerable and low income groups and most specifically it includes women communities [2]. The increased food production is leading to commercialization and hence it has greater impact on environment. Change in agricultural and land use pattern is leading to increase in global emission of Green House Gases (GHGs) by nearly 23.1 % [5]. In addition to this, there are much more pronounced catastrophic effects including loss of biodiversity, water deficit, soil degradation affecting the environment causing larger adverse impacts [3 a]. Faulty agricultural practices involving unsustainable use of natural resources and alteration of feeding habits draws greater economic costs which may deepen the food crisis [9]. Green revolution based agricultural trend with rampant use of fertilizers and pesticides produce unlimited runoffs bring adverse impact on human health. Poor communities involving mostly women, children and elderly are mostly vulnerable to food related poverty with intense food insecurity and malnutrition which is further worsened by climate crisis [3b]. Three major challenge putting immense pressure on human civilization which are supporting provision for food and nutrition security, sustaining livelihood, sustainable utilization of natural resources and resilience against climate change. Innovative technology implementation in agriculture and sustainable production by reducing land use can mitigate all the challenges and even can prevent global warming by reducing emission of green house gases which may reduce the crisis due to climate change [8].

Agricultural enterprise can scale to amazing success only by introducing the gender equality in agriculture. This is because women farmers have usually less access to land, resources, information, and credit facilities [5]. Currently, women are gaining priority in terms of their deployment in agriculture sector by imparting training, involving them in innovative technology as well as extension work to narrow down the gap to move forward towards gender equality [6]. This will strategically enhance the opportunity for women in related activities and can boost their performance and productivity too [1] More women involvement can make intensification of agriculture with the use of more chemical fertilizers and pesticides and hence more productive gain target will work as stressors to break sustainable framework in agriculture. It is very important to think about the gender equality through provide opportunity to women stake holders in sustainable way thorough introduction of innovative sustainable modern technologies.

Tribal populace is generally acquainted with conventional agriculture by their indigenous technical knowledge with the existing varieties of crops. These indigenous systems were not changed due to sustainable nature of their agriculture in traditional set up in tribal dominated regions of Koraput. The major crops cultivated include Paddy, Ragi and Maize. Tribal women were mostly engaged in family along with the males. Due to population

growth and increased demand for improvement of financial infrastructure they are trying to opt for the introduction of improved as well as resistant varieties and involved in cultivation, harvesting, food preparation and feeding and key players in the supply chain. Sustainable cereal cultivation is contributing towards employment generation, food, nutritional and livelihood security not only for the tribal women themselves but to their families and the vulnerable communities of the area. This is seems to be a bonus to the production due to Indigenous technical college involving use of traditional practices such as use of organic manures, bio-pesticides, crop rotation as a method of traditional methods of sustainable production.

Materials and Methods

2.1 Research sites

Our study included 16 tribal dominated revenue villages in 8 GPs and 4 blocks namely Koraput, Jeypore, Kundra and Boipariguda of Koraput district of Odisha. Two sampling sites (field) of tribal village taken in each GP of the respective blocks. The study was conducted from June 2022 to May 2023. In total, eight sampling fields areas area are taken for study of cultivation of three major cereals as Paddy (*Oryza sativa*), Maize (*Zea mays*) and Finger millet (*Eleusine coracana*) . Four different blocks of Koraput districts namely Koraput, Jeypore, Kundra and Baipariguda were taken for research study. Two GP in each in each block and and two villages in each GP were taken for field investigation with respect to different cereal crops. In total eight GPs and sixteen villages are included for doing field research with respect to different cereal crops. Umari and Mastiput GP of Koraput block, Dangorchucha and Patraput GP of Jeypore block, Kundra and Lima GP of Kundra block and Badaput and Mahuli GP of Boipariguda block were included. Crop field sites in sixteen blocks taken for research study are Machhara, Khiloput, Bagaraguda, Dongri maliguda, Bisoiput, Bodapar, Kanjai, Maliguda, Chendia jhilligam, Kaudiaguda, Kusumguda, Pradhaniguda, Kasiguda, Bhejaguda, Baliguda and Rauliguda.

2.2 Methods of data collection

Twelve women SHGs of six revenue blocks with 120 members those are directly or indirectly involved in cereal cultivation were interviewed with pre-structured questionnaire using PRA tools This is responsible for generating a comprehensive data in the present study.

2.3 Interventions studied in cereal cultivation

Two types intervention adopted by tribal communities. One with the use of indigenous technology with indigenous varieties. Other with combination of indigenous technology and improved and resistant varieties with modern sustainable technologies (Table 1).

2.4 Statistical analysis

Both the agricultural system analysed with reference to investment, production, gross value and net profit for three different crops. Three major cereals paddy, finger millet and maize analysed by two ways ANOVA using SPSS.

Results and discussion

Tribal communities almost fully depending on the agriculture for their food and nutrition security, socioeconomic stability and livelihood. Three major cereals as paddy, finger millet and maize are cultivated in the tribal dominated regions of Korput and constitute the major staples in the area. Tribal women are the major stake holders in within tribal communities. They contribute to child raising, household works as well as farming activities and involve in all stages of

agriculture (Fig.1,2,3 and 4). Due to increase in tribal population the demand for the major staples as cereals increased several fold. In addition, irregular weather pattern and climate change sometimes reducing major cereal productivity in the area and hence intensifying the crisis. Tribal communities since inception cultivating their local available indigenous varieties of cereals by applying Indigenous Technical Knowledge (ITK). The system adopted in regular trend was found to be very sustainable but fails to fulfill the increased demand for increased population.

Fig. 1. Women sowing seeds of finger millet Fig.2. Women planting rice in the field

Fig.3. A female farmer is clearing grasses Fig. 4. Female stake holders of tribal area

Three different crop varieties as rice, finger millet and maize showed different amount of invests per acre of land and it differs as investment cost includes Seed, planting material, labour charges, manure and fertilizers, irrigation and miscellaneous expenses. These expenses were found to be different. Investment for different crop variety and management were found to be different as it is varied between 8,500 per acre to 16,400 per acre. Production also identified to be different between different type crops. Net profits also found to be different where lowest profit shared for Maize and highest for finger millet (Table 1). Investment parameters, average production, gross value and profit shown in Fig.5,6 and 7 and 8 respectively.

Table. 1 Crop varieties with investments, production and Gross revenue and profit in cereal cultivation

SL.N.O	CROP	CROP VARIETY	Crop management	Investment(INR/acre)	Average Production (quintals/acre)	Gross value(INR/acre)	Profit (INR/acre)
1	Rice	Kola jira (Local)	ITK+Low fertilizer use +No chemical pesticide	12,276	19.2	36,480	24,204
		Swarna-sub 1 (High Yielding)	ITK+moderate fertiliser use +Moderate pesticide use in emergency	18,370	36.3	68,970	50,600
2	Millet	Bada mandi (Local)	ITK+Low fertilizer use +No chemical pesticide	8,500	14.6	40,880	32,380
		Bhairabi (High yielding)	ITK+ moderate fertiliser use+ Moderate pesticide use in emergency	11,500	25.9	72,520	61,020
3	Maize	Decan-109	ITK+Low fertilizer use +No chemical pesticide	13,200	13.1	24,890	11,690
		Madhuri	ITK+ moderate fertiliser use +Moderate pesticide use in emergency	16,400	18.4	34,960	18,560

It is evident from table both crop production and management statistically significant and corresponding 'F' values for crop and crop management were 130.862 and 191.478 with interaction value between them of 11.394 which was statistically significant at $p < 0.05$ (Table 2 and 2.1). The mean of ANOVAs shows between 10,000 to 15,323 (Table 2.2). CD values also significant with mean of 1348.077 and SE(m) of 362.709 (2.3). Similarly, ANOVA for Average production three crops shows 'F' value of interaction between crop and production is 185.866 which is statistical significant at the level of $p < 0.01$ (Table 3). Mean of the interaction between two showed that among the crop varied between 15.633 and 26.867 and mean of production between 15.750 and 27.750 (Table 3.1). C.D. and SE(m) are found to be 1.137 and 0.306 respectively (3.2). Similarly, ANOVA for Gross value for three crops shows 'F' value of interaction between crop and gross value is 426.851 which is statistical significant at the level of $p < 0.01$ (Table 4). Mean of the interaction between two showed that among the crop varied between 34,083.330 and 58,816.670 and mean of gross values between 29,925.000 and 56,700.000 (Table 4.1). C.D. and SE(m) are found to be 1,616.254 and 434.864 respectively (Table 4.2). Similarly, ANOVA for profit three crops shows 'F' value of interaction between crop and profit is 643.494 which is statistical significant at the level of $p < 0.01$ (Table 5). Mean of the interaction between two showed that among the crop varied between 23,091.330 and 43,393.330 and mean of profit between 15.750 and 27.750 (Table 5.1). C.D. and SE(m) are found to be 1,206.869 and 324.716 respectively (5.2).

Fig. 5. Investment

Fig.6. Average production

Fig. 7. Gross value

Fig.8. Profit

Table. 2 Analysis of Variance of crop and crop management and investment

Source of Variation	DF	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	F-Calculated	Significance
Replication	1	142,572.000			
Factor A-crop	2	68,863,810.667	34,431,905.333	130.862	0.00005
Factor B-crop management	1	50,380,812.000	50,380,812.000	191.478	0.00004
Interaction A X B	2	5,996,024.000	2,998,012.000	11.394	0.01373
Error	5	1,315,580.000	263,116.000		
Total	11	126,698,798.667			

Table. 2.1 Two Way Mean Table

	B1	B2	Mean A
A1	12,276.000	18,370.000	15,323.000
A2	8,500.000	11,500.000	10,000.000
A3	13,200.000	16,400.000	14,800.000
Mean B	11,325.330	15,423.330	

Table.2.2 Table of sem, sed and c.d.

Factors	C.D.	SE(d)	SE(m)
Factor(A)	953.235	362.709	256.474
Factor(B)	778.313	296.151	209.410
Factor(A X B)	1,348.077	512.948	362.709

Table. 3 Analysis of Variance of Average production

Source of Variation	DF	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	F-Calculated	Significance
Replication	1	4.563			
Factor A	2	294.000	147.000	784.824	0.00000
Factor B	1	378.563	378.563	2,021.125	0.00000
Interaction A X B	2	69.627	34.813	185.866	0.00002
Error	5	0.937	0.187		
Total	11	747.690			

Table. 3.1 Two Way Mean Table

	B1	B2	Mean A
A1	19.200	36.300	27.750
A2	14.600	25.900	20.250
A3	13.100	18.400	15.750
Mean B	15.633	26.867	

Table 3.2 table of sem, sed and c.d.

Factors	C.D.	SE(d)	SE(m)
Factor(A)	0.804	0.306	0.216
Factor(B)	0.657	0.250	0.177
Factor(A X B)	1.137	0.433	0.306

Table. 4 Analysis of Variance of Gross value

Source of Variation	DF	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	F-Calculated	Significance
Replication	1	3,328,533.333			
Factor A	2	1,670,055,000.000	835,027,500.000	2,207.821	0.00000
Factor B	1	1,835,213,333.333	1,835,213,333.333	4,852.323	0.00000
Interaction A X B	2	322,881,266.667	161,440,633.333	426.851	0.00000
Error	5	1,891,066.667	378,213.333		
Total	11	3,833,369,200.000			

Table 4.1 Two Way Mean

	B1	B2	Mean A
A1	36,480.000	68,970.000	52,725.000
A2	40,880.000	72,520.000	56,700.000
A3	24,890.000	34,960.000	29,925.000
Mean B	34,083.330	58,816.670	

Table 4.2 sem, sed and c.d.

Factors	C.D.	SE(d)	SE(m)
Factor(A)	1,142.864	434.864	307.495
Factor(B)	933.145	355.065	251.069
Factor(A X B)	1,616.254	614.991	434.864

Table. 5 Analysis of Variance of profit

Source of Variation	DF	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	F-Calculated	Significance
Replication	1	1,575,425.333			
Factor A	2	2,161,428,210.667	1,080,714,105.333	5,124.750	0.00000
Factor B	1	1,236,513,612.000	1,236,513,612.000	5,863.552	0.00000
Interaction A X B	2	271,401,704.000	135,700,852.000	643.494	0.00000
Error	5	1,054,406.667	210,881.333		
Total	11	3,671,973,358.667			

Table 5.1 Two Way Mean Table

	B1	B2	Mean A
A1	24,204.000	50,600.000	37,402.000
A2	33,380.000	61,020.000	47,200.000
A3	11,690.000	18,560.000	15,125.000
Mean B	23,091.330	43,393.330	

Table 5.2 sem, sed and c.d.

Factors	C.D.	SE(d)	SE(m)
Factor(A)	853.386	324.716	229.609
Factor(B)	696.786	265.130	187.475
Factor(A X B)	1,206.869	459.218	324.716

Conclusion

It has been observed that women of the rural area show emergence in the agriculture enterprises through their SHGs network. They are more inclined towards agriculture by introduction of modern innovative technologies in sustainable manner. They cannot leave their indigenous technical knowledge and trying to preserve the biodiversity in their locality. By conservation of indigenous technology if, the modern technology with introduction of resistance high yielding varieties will bring greater support to them in terms of enhancement of production without affecting their indigenous livelihood then they will acknowledge and adopt to change. It is on the part of researcher, stake holders (women farming communities) and policy makers to sit together to discuss regarding the inclusion of modern, innovative agricultural technology for sustainable production of cereals for sustainable livelihood.

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Data Availability Statement

The authors confirm that the data supports the findings of the study are available within the article and raw data supports the results are available with the authors will provide with request if needed. It is stated that the published publication includes all graphics and data collected or developed during the study.

Author's Contributions

All authors' contributions to the articles are indicated.

Mohanty Samir: Collected the research data, Photography

Biswal Nirmal Chandra: Statistical analysis of the data draft manuscript prepared,

Lenka Kartik Charan: Compilation of the manuscript as per the journal requirement and submission the article after finalised based on the feedback of all author's.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declared no potential conflicts of interest with respect to the research authorship/or publication of this article.

Ethics

There are no ethical issues with the publication of this manuscript

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